

To Evaluate Maternal Vitamin D Levels in Patients with Hypertensive Disorders of Pregnancy: A Case-Control Study

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to evaluate maternal vitamin D levels in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. The duration of the study was 2 years with a sample size of 120 case and 120 control subjects. One hundred twenty patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and satisfying the inclusion criteria were enrolled and profiled as a part of this study.

Results: In the present study, 240 women were included. 120 women who had hypertensive disorders of pregnancy were included as “cases” group and the other 120 women without any hypertensive disorders. Majority of women (83.34%) in hypertensive group had severe vitamin D deficiency as compared to 12.5% with moderate and 4.16% with mild deficiency of vitamin D. The difference among two groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Whereas among normotensive women only 3.34% had severe vitamin D deficiency, 75% had moderate deficiency and 16.66% had mild deficiency of vitamin D. The sub-classification of women on the basis of type of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was done and the majority of women. Serum vitamin D was determined for every participant.

Conclusion: Our study showed that serum vitamin D levels were low in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy as compared to normal normotensive pregnant women. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency was significant in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy as compared to normal normotensive pregnant women.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Hypertensive Disorders, Pregnancy, Preeclampsia

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Introduction

Beyond its well-established role in bone health, vitamin D has been studied as a potentially modifiable factor contributing to extra skeletal health during pregnancy. [1] During pregnancy, vitamin D may play a role in implantation and placental

function potentially due to angiogenic, immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory effects. [2]

Low circulating 25-hydroxyvitamin D levels are common in pregnant women. [3] The biologically active form of vitamin D,

1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 (calcitriol), can suppress renin biosynthesis and vascular smooth muscle cell proliferation, modulates macrophage activity and cytokine production, [4,5] and regulates transcription of genes linked to placental invasion, normal implantation, and angiogenesis. [2]

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy are the most common medical complication of pregnancy and its association with vitamin D deficiency is worth discussing. Hypertensive disorders accounts for potential maternal and perinatal risks and outcome. It includes gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, chronic hypertension, preeclampsia superimposed on chronic hypertension. Preeclampsia (PE) is a disease specific to pregnancy affecting many bodily systems. This is characterized by high blood pressure and proteinuria after the 20th week of pregnancy. This increases maternal and fetal mortality and morbidity. Different factors such as angiogenetic, endothelial dysfunction, syncytiotrophoblastic microparticles and inflammatory activation play an important role in the progression of preeclampsia. [6]

Apart from known risk factors such as stress, obesity, diabetes, and advanced age, low anti-oxidants, variations in trace metals and electrolyte disturbances have been linked with the pathogenesis of preeclampsia. [7,8] Knowledge of risk factors is important as treatment can be directed towards these for reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with this disorder. Epidemiological studies have shown the importance of vitamin D deficiency in the development of preeclampsia. [9] The importance of vitamin D deficiency in immunomodulation and placental development has been highlighted in various studies. So, they put the emphasis on vitamin D deficiency regarding its probable role in the physiology of preeclampsia. [10]

Vitamin D (sunshine vitamin) is a prohormone which plays significant role in bone metabolism via regulation of calcium and phosphate homeostasis, in addition to its neuromuscular functions. Vitamin D deficiency (VDD) is a global health care issue, with billion carrying deficiency or insufficiency around the world. In pregnancy, vitamin D status is important for maternal and fetal health. It is highly useful to assess vitamin D deficiency in mothers so that strategies can be implemented to prevent vitamin D deficiency in pregnancy and lactation.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate maternal vitamin D levels in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Patna medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. The duration of the study was 2 years with a sample size of 120 case and 120 control subjects. One hundred twenty patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and satisfying the inclusion criteria were enrolled and profiled as a part of this study.

Inclusion criteria

All pregnant women with hypertensive disorders admitted to PMCH in the mention term were included in the study.

Patients would have to meet the American college of obstetricians and gynaecology (ACOG) criteria for diagnosing hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg or systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or both).

Exclusion criteria

All pregnant women with multifetal gestation, epilepsy, bone disorders, any multivitamin intake, renal disease, liver disease, hemorrhagic disorders, thyroid disease or any endocrinal disease.

Control group

The control group in this study was 120 normotensive pregnant women with similar gestational age.

Procedure

Vein puncture technique was used to collect fasting blood samples. Quantitation of serum 25(OH) vitamin D [25(OH) D₂ plus 25(OH) D₃] was performed using the chemiluminescence method by Centaur XP in the biochemistry laboratory. This method can detect 25(OH) vitamin D in the range of 4.2-150 ng/ml. Calcium was measured by the use of the O-cresolphthalein complex using dimension by RXL. Parathormone was measured using chemiluminometric technology by Centaur XP. PTH assay was a 2-site sandwich immunoassay. Serum samples were drawn at similar gestational ages in both groups.

Screening/survey

A total of 130 women were screened, 7 were rejected to participate in the study and 3 were not fit according to inclusion criteria and finally, 120 women with hypertensive disorders during pregnancy were found fit according to inclusion criteria.

Quality control measure to check data completeness and consistency

Local and English language was preferred to ask the screening questions during the initial screening of patients with valid identity proof and also recorded the data. Study tools used were, case reporting forms and consent forms. After written informed consent form had been obtained, detailed history of the presenting symptoms and their onset was recorded. Detailed histories of all the women were obtained (like demographic, age of the patient, parity, last menstrual period, previous menstrual history) were noted on patient proforma. Each participant underwent an ultrasonographic

examination to estimate the gestational age, routine haemogram, and other biochemical investigations were carried out as and when required.

Confounders

Present demonstration of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was defined by diastolic Blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg or systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or both. The detailed history of women included; age, religion, literacy, occupation, residence, the socioeconomic status will be noted. Obstetrics history, past history, any history of previous pregnancy affected by HDP, family history, pre-existing medical conditions, gestational age, education, socioeconomic status and prenatal information.

Outcome variables

The outcome variables in current study were; to compare the maternal serum Vitamin D levels in patients with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and normotensive women and to compare the maternal and neonatal outcome in these patients.

Statistical analysis

The data was coded and entered into Microsoft excel spreadsheet. Analysis was done using Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20 (IBM SPSS Statistics Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) Windows software program. Descriptive statistics included computation of percentages, means and standard deviations. The unpaired t-test (for quantitative data to compare two independent two groups) and ANOVA test were used for quantitative data comparison of all clinical indicators. Chi-square test and fisher exact test were used for qualitative data whenever two or more than two groups were used to compare. Level of significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

Table 1: Demographic details of study groups

Demographic	Groups	
	Case n=120	Controls n=120
Age (years), N (%)		
19-25	70 (58.33)	80 (66.67)
26-31	40 (33.33)	35 (29.17)
31-37	7 (5.84)	3 (2.5)
>37	3 (2.5)	2 (1.66)
Area of residence, N (%)		
Urban	80 (66.66)	90 (75)
Rural	40 (33.34)	30 (25)
Employment status, N (%)		
Employed	50 (41.66)	60 (50)
Unemployed	70 (58.34)	60 (50)
Education, N (%)		
Illiterate	35 (29.16)	20 (16.66)
Literate	60 (50)	70 (58.34)
Graduation/post-graduation	25 (20.84)	30 (25)
Socioeconomic status, N (%)		
Upper	3 (2.5)	4 (3.34)
Upper middle	45 (37.5)	55 (45.84)
Lower middle	40 (33.34)	41 (34.16)
Lower	32 (26.16)	20 (16.66)
Gravida status, N (%)		
Primigravida	80 (66.66)	90 (75)
Multigravida	40 (33.34)	30 (25)
Mean	5.40±7.3	18.32±8.22

In the present study, 240 women were included. One hundred women who had hypertensive disorders of pregnancy were included as “cases” group and the other hundred women without any hypertensive disorders.

Table 2: Distribution of patients on the basis of vitamin D level

Distribution of patients	Groups	
	Case n=120 (%)	Controls n=120 (%)
Mild (10-20 ng/ml)	5 (4.16)	20 (16.66)
Moderate (5- 10 ng/ml)	15 (12.5)	90 (75)
Severe (<5 ng/ml)	100 (83.34)	10 (3.34)

Majority of women (83.34%) in hypertensive group had severe vitamin D deficiency as compared to 12.5% with moderate and 4.16% with mild deficiency of vitamin D. The difference among two groups was statistically significant

($p < 0.001$). Whereas among normotensive women only 3.34% had severe vitamin D deficiency, 75% had moderate deficiency and 16.66% had mild deficiency of vitamin D.

Table 3: Association of vitamin D deficiency with type of hypertension

Type of hypertension		Case n=120
Gestational Hypertension	Mild	5
	Moderate	6

	Severe	25
Chronic Hypertension	Mild	0
	Moderate	3
	Severe	15
Preeclampsia/Eclampsia	Mild	0
	Moderate	2
	Severe	50
Chronic hypertension with superimposed preclamsia	Mild	0
	Moderate	4
	Severe	10

The sub-classification of women on the basis of type of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was done and the majority of women. Serum vitamin D was determined for every participant.

Discussion

Maternal vitamin D deficiency is a widespread public health problem that is prevalent during pregnancy. Vitamin D acts in various physiological processes as vascular health, immune function, metabolism and function of the placenta. [11] Vitamin D has wide functions during pregnancy, including the effects on placental function and inflammatory response. [12]

Vitamin D (sunshine vitamin) has been studied as a potentially modifiable factor contributing to extra skeletal health during pregnancy.¹ Vitamin D deficiency is worldwide epidemic, with a prevalence that ranges from 18% to 84% depending on the country of residence, ethnicity, and local clothing customs and dietary intake. [1,13,14] Hypertension is the most common medical problem encountered during pregnancy complicating 5-10% of pregnancies. [15] Maternal vitamin D metabolism is altered during pregnancy, leading to increased circulating levels of both the vitamin D binding protein (VDBP) and the active metabolite, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (1,25(OH)₂D).

Clinical studies establishing an association between vitamin D levels and adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, and low birth weight,

preterm labor, and caesarean delivery have conflicting results. Data is sparse as regards the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy in India is concerned. [16]

In current study it was found that no women in hypertensive as well as normotensive group had normal serum vitamin D levels, all had same degree of vitamin D deficiency indicating the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in India. Sahu et al conducted a similar study where the mean serum vitamin D level was 9.06±5.20 ng/ml in diseased group as compared to 13.67±7.24 ng/ml in healthy pregnant group which was statistically significant (p<0.05) and exactly similar to the present study. [17] Mehta et al conducted a study also concluded vitamin D level is lower in women with HDP as compared to healthy pregnancy women also the level of vitamin D decreases with severity of HDP. [18] Similar to current study, Gupta et al found more incidence of severe vitamin D deficiency (90%) in preeclamptic patients as compared to normotensive patients (62%). [19]

Our study showed that serum vitamin D levels were low in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy with mean serum vitamin D level 5.40±7.3 ng/ml as compared to normal normotensive pregnant women 18.32±8.22 ng/ml. These findings were in accordance with Mehmood et al who found that serum 25(OH)-D concentration was significantly lower in cases (preeclampsia, eclampsia and gestational hypertension) compared to

controls. 6.78 ng/ml in cases and 9.43 ng/ml in controls (p=0.002). [20]

Women, who had hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, had significantly lower serum vitamin D levels as compared to normotensive pregnant ladies. Though, severity of vitamin D deficiency did not show any correlation with type of hypertensive disorder of pregnancy or maternal or neonatal complications. [21]

Conclusion

Our study showed that serum vitamin D levels were low in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy as compared to normal normotensive pregnant women. Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency was significant in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy as compared to normal normotensive pregnant women. So, it is suggested that maternal serum vitamin D level should be estimated in early pregnancy in all high-risk women. Supplementation of vitamin D in early pregnancy can effectively prevent pre-eclampsia and thus improve pregnancy outcome and bring down maternal morbidity and mortality.

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